

Overcoming Linguistic Challenges of Classical Hebrew (Biblia Hebraica) and Koine Greek Languages In Biblical Studies through AI Technology

David O. Alabi¹, Department of Philosophy and Religious Studies

Joseph Ayo Babalola University, Ikeji-Arakeji, Osun State

Emmanuel Tukasi², St Joseph Christian College, London

O J. Olufemi³, Joseph Ayo Babalola University, Ikeji-Arakeji, Osun State

doalabi@jubu.edu.ng¹

Corresponding author¹

Received: 15/04/2026; Accepted: 20/05/2026; Published: 26/06/2026

Abstract: This study examined the linguistic challenges of classical Hebrew (Biblia Hebraica) and Koine Greek in Biblical studies by introducing AI technology. This aimed to identify the challenges students face in learning Hebrew and Greek. It intended to identify students' preferences in studying the languages through AI technology in higher institutions and identify possible effect(s) of learning Hebrew and Greek languages through AI technology. Given the growing significance of artificial intelligence in pedagogy, it was observed that the use of AI as a technological tool for studying classical Hebrew and Koine Greek in biblical studies has yet to receive adequate attention from researchers. Using the Snowball Sampling Technique, 50 undergraduate students as well as 50 postgraduate students were interviewed. A pretested, structured questionnaire was administered via an online Google Form. Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed for the analysis. Findings revealed that most postgraduate students prefer to study Greek, while a quarter wished to avoid studying both languages. Eight difficulties were identified among respondents, of which mastering the numerous clauses, especially in Hebrew, ranked highest in importance. Identified preferences in using AI include that instructors must be friendly, interactive, and ready to provide periodic assessments for students. The seventeen hypothesized possible effects of learning Hebrew and Greek languages through AI technology were all asymptotically significant at 1.00%. The study recommended developing software to address the numerous challenges students face in learning the third and fourth languages, as identified.

Keywords: *Linguistics, Challenges, Learning, Hebrew, Greek, Artificial Intelligence*

INTRODUCTION

Biblical Studies entail the study and teaching of both the Old and New Testaments as sacred texts, as well as related issues. The essence of biblical teaching and learning is, in part, to grasp the divine message sent by God and delivered by the prophets to ancient Israel and, by extension, to the entire human race. The biblical teaching, from the Mosaic era to the Deuteronomistic period and to Rabbinic teaching in the Old Testament, is anchored in the preservation of classical Hebrew. After the Babylonian captivity and during the Persian Empire, the translators of the Holy Bible used Koine Greek to extend the message to Greek audiences and the people of the new empire. Jesus Christ, the New Testament writers, and apostolic missionaries in the Mediterranean world extensively explored these language opportunities. It should be appreciated that both testaments were written in ancient languages. Biblia Hebraica, meaning the Hebrew Bible, which is the Christian Old Testament, was originally and principally written in classical Hebrew. It was written without vowel letters until the Masoretes invented the vowels (Alabi, 2024). The second language of OT writing was Aramaic, especially during the exilic era. Classical Hebrew was one of the ancient Semitic languages. Classical Hebrew provided the bedrock for modern spoken Hebrew used by contemporary Israelis. It started with symbols, then syllables

and pronunciation, before final written forms. Ancient peoples invented symbols to express their thoughts and to document what they considered vital.

The Greek language, on the other hand, is also ancient. The language flourished during the reign of Alexander the Great, who ruled between 336 and 323 BCE. There were dialectic types of the language, such as Attic, Aeolic, Doric, Ionic, and others. During the Hellenistic era, another dialect known as Koine, meaning common, evolved. The dialect became the language of the New Testament (NT) era and NT texts by the Apostles. It was easy for the apostles, early Christians, and early church missionaries to propagate the gospel of the Lord Jesus Christ throughout the Mediterranean world in Koine Greek, due to the Hellenism initiated by Alexander the Great.

The significance of teaching and learning the original languages of the Bible, Hebrew and Greek, is best understood in the accuracy and nuanced interpretation derived from studying the Scriptures. The efforts of translators to make biblical texts accessible in the Vulgate, Peshitta, Septuagint–LXX, Samaritan, English, Yoruba, Hausa, Igbo, and other versions are highly commendable. Currently, the Holy Bible has been translated into 756 languages (Wycliffe Global Alliance, 2025). Translation into these languages has been helpful; however, the richness and depths of the original texts are most often lost during translation and comprehension exercises. Thus, studying the bible in its original language remains essential.

In Nigeria, learning Hebrew and Greek entails the use of the second language, that is, English, designated as L2; the first language being the native language or mother tongue, designated as L1; and the third and fourth languages designated as L3 and L4, respectively. As pointed out by Gajendra (2018), language is universal, and everybody uses it and wants to use it aptly. The identified challenges in learning a second language were age, social factors, psychological factors, the availability of teaching aids, a monolingual instructor, and interference from the mother tongue (Gajendra, 2018). Similarly, the above-mentioned identified challenges are also applicable to learning L3 and L4.

Overcoming these and many other linguistic challenges entails developing a set of strategies targeted at improving language skills, enhancing communication, and fostering cultural understanding. In addition, learning L3 and/or L4 entails using clear, simple language and seeking translation services in a conducive learning environment. In view of this, the strategy must address challenges associated with vocabulary memorization, transliterations, translations, development, grammatical construction, correct pronunciation, as well as bridging the gap created by cultural differences. Specifically, strategies must include utilizing visual-audio aids, simplifying language, providing comprehensible input, and fostering a supportive learning environment. Furthermore, the strategy must be simple, engaging, and interactive to allay fears and instil confidence, thereby enabling success more easily.

A brilliant strategy that could offer a personalized learning experience, with the use of automated administrative tasks, and further provide data-driven insights, must be technology-driven. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the technology that enables computers and machines to simulate human learning, comprehension, problem-solving, decision-making, creativity, and autonomy (IBM, 2025). It is the theory and development of computer systems capable of performing tasks

that historically required human intelligence, such as recognizing speech, making decisions, and identifying patterns. AI is an umbrella term encompassing a wide range of technologies, including machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing (NLP) (Courser, 2025).

The advantages of employing AI in solving challenges in learning biblical Hebrew and Koine Greek languages include, among many, around-the-clock access to learning resources and support, the ability to address learning gaps, and the ability to inspire students to generate ideas and solutions, fostering creativity and innovation.

The problem of the study bordered on the complaints, linguistic phobias of the learners, the unusual character, memorization of the two strange vocabularies, and irregular tenses of both have not been addressed with the aid of Artificial Intelligence. Hebrew and Greek are languages in biblical studies that must be studied as courses within the umbrella of languages, grammar, and literature in biblical disciplines. The use of a second language to teach and learn these third and fourth languages, coupled with the preconceived notion among students that both are hard to learn and understand during their orientation and training, poses academic threats to pedagogy and its applicability. Specifically, the linguistic challenge starts with recognizing, mastering, and writing Hebrew and Greek alphabets, declensions of the indicatives, parsing the words, memorization of vocabularies, syntax, semantics, phonology, morphology, and most especially the dynamic, incessant changing and irregular tenses in Greek and the rest. Experiences have shown that young scholars avoid studying Biblical Studies at the postgraduate level due to the perceived challenges posed by these languages. Many complained that the languages are hard to learn: “I cannot cope,” “I don’t understand,” “I only managed to pass it,” “I crammed and poured it down to pass.” These are the complaints of many postgraduate candidates. Thus, many upcoming biblical scholars at the postgraduate level and many incoming scholars turn to other areas of specialisation, such as African Traditional Religion (ATR), Church History, Comparative Religion, Philosophy of Religion, Sociology of Religion, and so on, because of these preconceived ideas.

Besides, in light of the increasing significance of artificial intelligence in pedagogy, which is transforming education by offering personalised learning experiences, automating administrative tasks, and providing data-driven insights, AI tools can become attuned to a student's specific needs in learning these biblical languages. Therefore, AI enables language instructors to provide professional, supplementary support to students, thereby enhancing efficiency. In the foregoing, it is observed that the use of artificial intelligence as a technological tool for studying classical Hebrew and Koine Greek in Biblical Studies has yet to receive adequate attention among researchers. Similarly, a study that identifies the merits of AI with respect to Biblical studies is yet to be in place. Thus, this study sought to address this gap by examining how AI technology can overcome the linguistic challenges posed by classical Hebrew (Biblia Hebraica) and Koine Greek in Biblical Studies.

The purpose of the study was to examine how AI technology can address the linguistic challenges posed by classical Hebrew (Biblia Hebraica) and Koine Greek in Biblical Studies. Specifically, the objectives were to: (i) identify challenges faced by students in learning Hebrew and Greek languages; (ii) identify students’ preferences in studying the languages through AI technology in

higher institutions; and (iii) identify possible effect(s) of learning Hebrew and Greek languages with the support of AI technology.

The research method used was a survey research method, with a structured interview employed to obtain information from Biblical Studies students. The tool used was a pre-tested structured questionnaire. Using snowball sampling, 50 undergraduate and 50 postgraduate students were interviewed. The analytical method employed for this study includes historical and descriptive analyses.

The significance of this study lies in the ease that both tutors and learners would derive from the introduction of AI. Studies on artificial intelligence are increasingly important not only in academic circles but also in the agricultural, banking, industrial, legal, and religious sectors. It is encouraging to recognise students' potential interest in learning languages through the introduction of AI. The rigour of studying the 3rd and 4th languages alongside the second language, English, will be reduced. Thus, it will allay students' phobia of studying languages at all levels, thereby fostering continuity in Biblical Studies among students, lecturers, and institutions. The future of Biblical Studies, in particular the original languages in which the sacred texts were written, must be secured. This is a necessity in religious studies and disciplines that must be sustained through the introduction of AI technology.

This study was premised on the Yoruba theory of Iwalaaye, that which must necessarily exist and live. This theory rests on the necessity of living and avoiding extinction. Hebrew and Greek were among the ancient languages of the Ancient Near East. They are living languages to date. The existentialist call for the study of these two ancient languages rests with scholars of Biblical Discipline, under the broad umbrella of Religious Studies. If they are not considered a matter of necessity, they will soon go extinct in Biblical Studies circles. The Hebrew language is a member of the extensive Semitic language family (Lambdin, 1971, 2021). These Semitic languages include Babylonian, Assyrian-Akkadian, Ancient Arabic and Ethiopian, Aramaic, Canaanite-Ugaritic, Phoenician and ancient Hebrew languages (Alabi, 2025).

The knowledge we have today of biblical Hebrew depends on Jewish oral traditions. Masoretes are acknowledged as those who introduced vowels to the original consonantal-dominated Hebrew alphabet and letters in the early years. While other nations preserve their native tongues and languages in many forms, biblical Hebrew of the Old Testament and Koine Greek depend on study within Biblical Studies in the faculty of Arts and in Departments, where Religious Studies are domiciled in various universities. Therefore, the languages must live for posterity in the biblical studies discipline.

Empirical Review

Kermanidis and others (2025) conducted a study on ICT adoption in education. The study explored topic identification using text analysis techniques in Modern Greek interviews with parents of students with functional diversity during Emergency Remote Teaching. The analysis focused on identifying key educational themes and addressing challenges in processing Greek educational data. Machine learning models, combined with Natural Language Processing

techniques, were applied to topic identification, using cross-validation and data balancing to enhance reliability.

The findings revealed the impact of linguistic complexity on topic modeling and highlighted the educational implications of analyzing qualitative data in this context. Among the models tested, the Naïve Bayes (Kernel) algorithm performed best when combined with lemmatization-based preprocessing, confirming that text normalization significantly enhances classification accuracy in Greek educational data. Sriram & Anburaj (2024) worked on language barriers in universities. The paper proposed strategies to mitigate language barriers in universities, such as inclusive teaching methods, improved language support systems, and the fostering of cultural awareness. In addition, it provided a framework for creating an inclusive academic environment where all students, regardless of their linguistic background, can thrive both academically and socially.

Elrod (2023) studied Biblical Hebrew in the Era of Generative Pre-trained AI. His work examined the potential impact of generative artificial intelligence, specifically OpenAI's GPT, on biblical studies, particularly biblical Hebrew. The study revealed that understanding the capabilities and potential trajectories of these technologies is vital to biblical Hebrew scholarship, as they already have the capacity to disrupt established scholarly norms and democratize access to advanced tools.

Ìwàláàyè Theory, Biblical Language and Artificial Intelligence

Ìwàláàyè, in the Yoruba language and worldview, fundamentally refers to being alive, the state of living, and existence in the world. The word is derived from two words, “ìwà”, the ontological sense of “being”, and láàyè, meaning “to be in the world” or “to have life.” This existential grounding provides a framework for thinking about biblical languages in the present age. Any language that is no longer read, spoken, or studied has lost its living presence, even if it survives in manuscripts or databases. Once it is no longer in the minds and practices of the people, it has lost its ìwàláàyè.

Biblical Hebrew, Koine Greek, and Aramaic demand active learning, disciplined exegesis, interpretation, and continuous scholarly transmission and translation to remain intellectually and religiously relevant. Under the concept of ìwàláàyè, the preservation of languages means keeping languages actively studied, interpreted, and taught within scholarly and faith communities. However, the gap between when these languages were used and the contemporary era may discourage students from learning them. Artificial intelligence is a tool that can strengthen biblical language learning by breaking down concepts, tagging semantics, analysing texts, and improving students' access to learning materials. This will keep the languages alive, and the ìwàláàyè theory is relevant here.

Demographic Characteristics of Sampled Respondents

The demographic characteristics of sampled respondents are presented in Table 1. It shows that sampled respondents were married (95.00%) and mostly male (96.00%). The modal class for age distribution was respondents between the age bracket 41 and 50; almost half of the respondents were graduates with a B.A or B.Th. equivalent (49.00%) in either Religious Studies or Theology. Most of the sampled respondents were postgraduate students (60.00%) whose area of specialization is Biblical Studies (34.00%). Besides, more than one-third of the sampled

respondents preferred to study Greek (40.00%), while 18.00% preferred Hebrew; about 26.00% showed interest in studying both languages, while 16.00% indicated that they had no interest in studying any of the languages. Reasons given by most respondents for not choosing Biblical languages include the following: “languages are hard to study” (06.00%), “I wish to avoid the languages” (25.00%), “there is no good tutor” (08.00%), “I managed to pass it last time” (08.00%) and “it is not the area of my interest” (18.00%). This result is presented in Table 2, titled "Preferred Language among Sampled Respondents."

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Sampled Respondents

S/No	Demographic Characteristic	Variables	Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	Sex	Male	96	96.00
		Female	04	04.00
		Total	100	100.00
2	Age	21 – 30	02	02.00
		31 – 40	13	13.00
		41 – 50	39	39.00
		51 – 60	35	35.00
		61 – 70	11	11.00
		71 >	00	00.00
		Total	100	100.00
3	Marital Status	Singles	03	03.00
		Married	95	95.00
		Separated	01	01.00
		Widow(er)	01	01.00
		Total	100	100.00
4	Educational Attainment	Certificate	05	05.00
		Diploma	11	11.00
		B.A./B.Th.	49	49.00
		M.A./M.Th.	28	28.00
		PhD	07	07.00
		Total	100	100.00
5	Degree in View	Certificate	04	04.00
		Diploma	02	02.00
		B.A./B.Th.	18	18.00
		M.A./M.Th.	41	41.00
		PhD	19	19.00
		No Response	16	16.00
		Total	100	100.00
6	Area of Specialization	Church History	22	22.00
		ATR	02	02.00
		Biblical Studies	34	34.00
		Sociology of Religion	08	08.00
		Philosophy of Religion	13	13.00

S/No	Demographic Characteristic	Variables	Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
		Comparative Religion	04	04.00
		Christian Theology	07	07.00
		Others	10	10.00
		Total	100	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 2: Preferred Language among Sampled Respondents

S/No	Variable	Response	Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	Reasons for not choosing Biblical Studies	It is hard	06	06.00
		I wish to avoid the languages	25	25.00
		There is no good tutor	08	08.00
		I managed to pass it last time	08	08.00
		Area of interest differs	18	18.00
		Others	09	09.00
		No response	26	26.00
		Total	100	100.00
2	Preferred Language	None	16	16.00
		Hebrews	18	18.00
		Greek	40	40.00
		Both	26	26.00
		Total	100	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2025

Identified Challenges Faced by Students in Learning Hebrew and Greek Languages

Table 3 presents the challenges identified by students in learning Hebrew and Greek. It was observed that most respondents agreed that recognising (56.00%) and writing (48.00%) the Hebrew and Greek alphabets are difficult for them. Explicitly, identified difficulties among respondents in learning the languages in order of importance are as follows: mastering the numerous clauses, especially in Hebrews (75.00%), learning syntax (68.00%), morphology (62.00%), recognizing the genders in words and sentences (59.00%), mastering the irregular tenses of the two languages (58.00%), learning semantics (53.00%), phonology (49.00%) as well as memorizing the vocabularies (49.00%). In Bible Colleges and Theological Seminaries, many seminarians are afraid of these Ancient Near Eastern languages.

Partly, the reasons deduced for this could stem from their ideas about their areas of calling and gifting. Some claimed that they were called to be Evangelists, Missionaries, Prophets, Pastors, deliverance ministers, and so on, and they do not need these classical languages. To sound funny, quite a number of these seminarians would say thus: "Life realities and human challenges and spirit-related problems do not listen to Hebrew and Greek but to the power of the Holy Spirit and great anointing". With this inherent notion, they disdained the learning of these languages. Many of the candidates have their spirits tuned away from acquiring knowledge of biblical texts. They focus, rather, on counting their days in Bible Colleges and Theological Seminaries to obtain

certificates and return to the originating church assemblies. One of the resulting effects of this shortcoming is poor exegetical and hermeneutical expositions of biblical texts in the church and before congregants.

Table 3: Challenges identified by students in learning Hebrew and Greek

S/No	What are the areas you find difficult in learning Hebrew or Greek?	Yes	No	No Response
(a)	Recognizing the alphabets	31	56	13
(b)	Writing the alphabets	34	48	18
(c)	Memorizing the vocabularies	49	34	17
(d)	Proper pronunciation, i.e., phonology	49	35	16
(e)	Mastering the tenses	58	25	17
(f)	Recognizing the genders in words and sentences	59	24	17
(g)	Syntax, i.e., learning grammar and constructing sentences	68	18	14
(h)	Semantics, i.e., learning the meaning and how words relate	53	29	18
(i)	Morphology, i.e., learning rules guiding word formation	62	22	16
(j)	Mastering the numerous clauses, especially in Hebrew	75	16	09

Source: Field survey, 2025

Identified Preferences in Studying Biblical Languages through AI Technology in Higher Institutions

Studying biblical languages among postgraduate students requires tenacity, persistence and diligence. However, instructors also have some basic roles to play in fostering knowledge. The study identified some preferences among students regarding whether AI technology will be effective; these are reported in order of importance: instructors must be friendly (93.00%), interactive (87.00%), and ready to provide periodic assessments for students (87.00%). In addition, instructors must be ready to assist with proper pronunciation (86.00%), assist students in mastering the case system (85.00%), and occasionally provide word etymology (83.00%). Moreover, instructors must be ready to offer individualised attention and support (79.00%), employ audible and colourful audiovisual aids (76.00%), and provide historical support to assist in knowledge retention (74.00%). The above result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Identified preferences in studying the languages through AI technology in higher institutions

S/N	If you are to learn Hebrew or Greek using AI, what are your preferences	Yes	No	No Response
(i)	The instructor must be friendly	93	2	5
(ii)	The instructor must be interactive	87	4	09
(iii)	The instructor must employ audio-visual aids (audible and colourful)	76	11	13
(iv)	The instructor must be ready to offer individualized attention and support	79	8	13
(v)	The instructor must be ready to assist in mastering the case system	85	5	10
(vi)	The instructor must be ready to assist in proper	86	5	09

	pronunciation			
(vii)	The instructor must be ready to provide historical support to assist in knowledge retention	74	14	12
(viii)	The instructor must be ready to provide periodic assessment	87	3	10
(ix)	The instructor must be ready to provide etymology of words occasionally	83	6	11

Identified Possible Effect(s) of Learning Hebrew and Greek Languages through AI Technology

The results of the Chi-Square test for the seventeen hypotheses about the possible effect(s) of learning the Hebrew and Greek languages through AI technology in the study area ranged from 26.000 to 100.880, with degrees of freedom ranging from 2 to 4, and the asymptotic significance was 0.000. The Chi-Square test was significant at the 1.00% confidence level for the seventeen hypotheses. Since the calculated Chi-Squares were greater than the tabulated Chi-Squares, the null hypotheses were rejected, and these statements were accepted: learning the languages through AI technology may yield the following effects

- i. Hebrew and Greek will become easier to understand.
- ii. Learning Hebrew and Greek will become more interesting.
- iii. Learning Hebrew and Greek will become practically interactive.
- iv. AI Technology will allay the phobia for studying languages among students at all levels.
- v. AI Technology will foster continuity in the areas of Biblical Studies among postgraduate students.
- vi. AI Technology will address the specific needs of Hebrew and Greek students.
- vii. AI Technology will provide automated learning steps for Hebrew and Greek students.
- viii. AI Technology application will keep improving as feedback is received from users, making it more effective.
- ix. AI technology may be expensive through data consumption, but it is accessible.
- x. Hebrew and Greek tutors may discourage students from using the application since job loss is looming. However, they cannot deny its relevance and importance in learning the two languages.
- xi. Students may become lazy in learning the language since there is no human supervision, but it is outside the conventional lecture rooms and enhances self-tutoring.
- xii. AI technology allays academic threats from the tutors or classroom tension and phobias, since you are the one teaching and learning by yourself with the aid of AI.
- xiii. Students will still run away from learning the language because it is hard, but persistence will see them through.
- xiv. Students will also rely on the application, thereby serving as an addition to the classroom lectures.
- xv. This may reduce the rate of failing tests and examinations in the Hebrew and Greek languages.
- xvi. The application may occupy large spaces in computers and androids, making it difficult to install.
- xvii. Tutors may stop providing professional and additional support needed by the students due to the availability of AI Technology.
- xviii. AI Technology can never remove memorizing the alphabet and vocabulary.

xix. AI Technology applications will keep requesting updated versions from time to time.

Table 5: Test Statistics on Data Obtained on Identified Possible Effect(s) of Learning Hebrew and Greek Languages through AI Technology

Variables	Chi-Square	Degree of freedom	Asymptotic Significance
v1	91.280 ^a	3	0.000
v2	72.560 ^a	3	0.000
v3	67.600 ^a	3	0.000
v4	55.760 ^a	3	0.000
v5	68.400 ^a	3	0.000
v6	61.360 ^a	3	0.000
v7	45.980 ^b	2	0.000
v8	30.980 ^b	2	0.000
v9	62.400 ^c	4	0.000
v10	51.700 ^c	4	0.000
v11	55.300 ^c	4	0.000
v12	42.200 ^c	4	0.000
v13	45.300 ^c	4	0.000
v14	36.900 ^c	4	0.000
v15	26.000 ^a	3	0.000
v16	58.400 ^a	3	0.000
v17	100.880 ^a	3	0.000

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 25.0.

b. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 33.3.

c. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 20.0.

Source: Field survey, 2025

CONCLUSION

This study examined overcoming linguistic challenges of classical Hebrew (Biblia Hebraica) and Koine Greek languages in Biblical studies by using AI technology. It revealed that most postgraduate students prefer to study Greek, while a quarter wish to avoid studying the languages. Eight difficulties were identified among respondents, with mastering numerous clauses, especially in Hebrew, ranking highest in importance. Identified preferences in using AI include that instructors must be friendly and interactive and be ready to provide periodic assessments for students. The seventeen hypothesized possible effects of learning Hebrew and Greek languages through AI technology were all asymptotically significant. The study recommended developing software to address numerous challenges students face in learning L3 and L4 through L2.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study therefore recommended that conventional tutors of these important languages should go the extra mile to make the teaching and learning of languages more interesting to learners at all levels. This is a pivotal way of securing the Iwalaaye, the sustainability of the essential languages in Biblical Studies as a discipline. Tutors should be friendly with learners and ensure simple delivery of lectures on the languages. They should remember that some people taught them while they were learning the languages. They should see learners as carriers of their success and profession to the future generation of Biblical Studies. Learners, on the other hand, should know that others have acquired the knowledge and gone through what they are learning, and that it is possible for them to gain mastery of the languages. It takes intentionality and persistence to overcome the challenges ahead as they learn the languages.

With the introduction of AI technology, learners should develop greater interest in Hebrew and Greek to ensure the longevity of their careers and success in life. Biblical Studies that focus on the Old and New Testaments could only be sustained with the bedrock of the understanding of the rudimentary knowledge of these two languages. AI technology is a valuable tool available to them, so they should incorporate it into their learning system and see it as an aid in learning difficult subjects, including biblical languages.

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